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Roadmaps for the establishment of National Building Renovation Plans

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Abstract. Renovating existing building stock is a critical step for mitigating climate change. While all EU Member States have developed Long Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS), the newly revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) mandates the transformation of these strategies into comprehensive National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP). These plans must include national targets in a unified and comparable format, outline investment needs, and provide an overview of relevant policies. To ensure consistency, the EPBD requires that the information in the NBRP be communicated using harmonized templates. This study presents a checklist-based methodological framework, derived directly from the EPBD's mandatory templates, to assess current LTRS and identify necessary improvements for their alignment with EPBD requirements in the development of comprehensive NBRP. The evaluation results are graphically summarized. The research was conducted within the LIFE23-CET-GreenRenoV8 project, which promotes sustainable renovation of the European building stock and provides methodological support for EPBD implementation across Europe. National partners from Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Greece, Slovenia, and Spain served as case studies, which allowed for the assessment of diverse building stock characteristics and a broad representation of European challenges. Each partner analysed and reviewed the data for their respective country, ensuring both national relevance and methodological rigor.

1. Introduction

The decarbonisation of the built environment is critical when it comes to reaching climate targets and policy goals established in the Paris Agreement to limit the increase in global temperature. To address this, the European Union has introduced various regulations and policies initially prioritizing energy efficiency in new construction but now increasingly focusing on renovation of the existing building stock [1, 2]. This shift stems from the recognition that 75% of the existing

EU's buildings is energy-inefficient, with 35% of it being over 50 years old [3]. Renovating these buildings offers a critical pathway to reduce operational and embodied emissions [4].

Under the European Green Deal, the Commission has developed a series of proposals to support the development of actions, policies and funding for the transition towards climate neutrality [1, 5]. Within this framework, the legislative package "Fit for 55", has tasked EU member states (MS) with reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels [6]. To meet these targets, emissions from buildings must be reduced by 60% and their final energy consumption by 14% [7], which is only possible through the renovation of existing buildings. However, the current annual renovation rate of 1% across Europe is highly insufficient to fulfil established decarbonization goals [2], and must be at least doubled each year until 2030 [8].

In the latest revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Commission is setting requirements and providing support to increase the renovation efforts throughout the union [9]. Each MS is tasked with the establishment of National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP) which must provide a roadmap supported by measurable indicators for the progressive renovation of the building stock to reach the 2050 goal of a zero-emission European built stock [4, 10]. Targets for 2030, 2040 and 2050 must be clarified, with an enhanced focus on upgrading the lowest performing buildings and decreasing the average primary energy use of buildings overall.

The development of NBRP is the culmination of a series of interconnected European Union policies, strategies, and legislative measures aimed at transforming the EU's building stock into a highly energy-efficient and decarbonized sector by 2050 [11]. The following Figure 1 visually maps out this evolution, highlighting how key initiative builds upon its predecessor to create a comprehensive policy framework.

Figure 1. Evolution of EU building policy: key strategies, directives, and milestones leading to national renovation plans.

The NBRP represent an advanced iteration of the Long-Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS), which were first introduced in the 2018 revision of the EPBD requiring all MS to submit their national LTRS by 2020 [12]. For the development of LTRS, the EPBD provided an optional template

to be followed by the contributing nations. Through 2020 to 2024 the EPBD underwent a major revision [4] that included a more robust and structured approach that builds upon and further details the LTRS while transforming its previous strategic framework into implementation plans, namely the NBRP. Each MS shall address gaps from previous LTRS and replace it with renovation plans that set the roadmap for a decarbonised built stock by 2050. These must include detailed national policies, financing mechanisms, and investment needs to increase the systematic renovation of the building stock. Each MS must submit the first draft of the NBRP by the end of 2025, with the final plan due by the end of 2026 [4]. Subsequent updates of national renovation plans - along with a detailed report on the implementation and achievement of national targets - must be submitted every 5 years, in alignment with the cycle of the National Energy and Climate Plans [13].

To enable implementation of the NBRP, the revised EPBD provides and mandates that the MS adhere to a standardized template set out in Annex II of the Directive. The mandatory use of this template aims to ensure consistency and comparability for the communication of the different national plans [4]. This decision aligns with research findings on the implementation of previous LTRS, which reveals that MS that did not adhere to the optional template structure recommended by the EPBD were more likely to submit plans with omissions or incomplete information [14].

To ensure alignment with the mandatory requirements of the EPBD, this study examines the current LTRS of Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Greece, Slovenia, and Spain and analyses their components to identify areas where further enhancement is needed for compliance and effective implementation of NBRP. When available, the study also reviews the latest progress of NBRP development in these countries.

By benchmarking previous LTRS against the EPBD's standardized NBRP template and tracking its latest implementation progress, this study aims to improve the quality, comparability, and transparency of renovation strategies across the EU. It also supports consistent data collection and regular updates, providing a harmonized and current overview of national plans as they evolve, thereby promoting cross-border consistency in achieving decarbonization targets.

The MS participating in this study are active partners in the LIFE23-CET-GreenRenoV8 project. Their contributions are driven by the shared commitment to supporting EPBD implementation and captures the diversity of regulatory frameworks, providing wide-ranging insights applicable across Europe. The GreenRenoV8 project itself delivers methodological support for EPBD implementation while advancing sustainable renovation of buildings. The project focusses on combining energy efficiency upgrades with seismic resilience through a cost-effective approach.

3. Methodology

The research comprised three main stages: first, a checklist-based methodological framework was developed; second, this framework was applied to review national LTRS and, when available, the latest NBRP updates within the case studies; third, the findings were visually represented through graphical summaries. The study concludes with an integrated overview and discussion of the outcomes.

Various methodological approaches have been used in previous studies to assess European national building renovation policies [1, 14, 15, 16, 17]. However, studies predominantly focus on general compliance of LTRS rather than tackling their transition to NBRP. Addressing this gap, the study applies a systematic checklist-based framework for analysing and benchmarking LTRS and NBRP through case studies from partner MS.

The checklist-based framework was directly derived from the Annex II of the EPBD [4], which comprises a standardized template for NBRP development. Each mandatory item in the template was converted into a checkbox categorized as “adequate,” “incomplete,” or “missing.” This categorisation is based solely on the presence of the mandatory items on the assessment, not on their quality. Both the existing LTRS and the most recent NBRP progress were evaluated using this checklist.

Data for completing the checklist was collected and reviewed by each case study partner using a comprehensive, harmonized Excel table distributed among the corresponding authors. Each partner evaluated and verified the data for their respective country, ensuring national relevance and methodological rigor while capturing a wide range of European policy frameworks. Data sources vary according to each country’s context but consistently include overviews on national LTRS and, when available, documents reflecting the most recent updates on NBRP development.

The national findings derived from the checklist evaluation were visualized through graphs, where each mandatory item in the Annex II of the EPBD (NBRP template) [4], is depicted as a vertical line. Every checklist entry is coded, matching the specific mandatory requirement in the NBRP template; detailed code descriptions and corresponding items are provided in the appendix. The results for both LTRS and current NBRP developments are illustrated as parallel points, categorized into “adequate,” “incomplete,” or “missing,” which form the graph’s background buffer zones. Ideally, a fully compliant NBRP assessment would be represented by a single line positioned in the “adequate” zone, highlighted by a reference dashed line on the graph. This visualization approach facilitates straightforward, cross-country comparison of assessment results, as well as direct intra-national comparison between national LTRS and NBRP outputs.

4. Results

Austria :

Figure 2. Visualization of the checklist-based evaluation of Austria for Long Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS, circles) and National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP, diamonds). Each vertical line represents a mandatory item delineated in the Annex II of the EPBD in the template for the development of NBRP. The x-axis presents each item’s code; descriptions and corresponding items are provided in the appendix. Results are displayed as points positioned within “adequate,” “incomplete,” or “missing” zones. The dashed line in the “adequate” zone indicates ideal compliance.

Due to the absence of a recent update to the LTRS for Flanders, the revised NECP has been used as the primary reference document for the completion of the checklist. In recent years efforts have been made to improve the documentation of the Flemish building stock, notably through data made available in the ‘Energiekaart Vlaanderen’ [19] which provides valuable insight in the internal update on the LTRS. This current study reveals substantial progress in aligning the Flemish LTRS with Annex II of the revised EPBD [4], particularly regarding building stock documentation and the integration of various data initiatives. This can be seen on the left-hand side of Figure 3, where a significant amount of missing LTRS items have been marked as adequate in the recent NBRP developments. Nevertheless, gaps persist, including insufficient information on the identification of the worst-performing buildings, current and target renovation rates, and the absence of clear guidelines for exempted buildings or detailed energy factors within existing roadmaps.

Greece:

Figure 4. Visualization of the checklist-based evaluation of Greece for Long Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS, circles) and National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP, diamonds). Each vertical line represents a mandatory item delineated in the Annex II of the EPBD in the template for the development of NBRP. The x-axis presents each item’s code; descriptions and corresponding items are provided in the appendix. Results are displayed as points positioned within “adequate,” “incomplete,” or “missing” zones. The dashed line in the “adequate” zone indicates ideal compliance.

The assessment of Greece’s LTRS was conducted through a review of official documents and mainly with an overview of the 2021 Greek Government Gazette (Issue B’ 974/12.03.2021) [20] and the mandatory requirements outlined in the EPBD template for national renovation plans [4]. Finally, the 2024 Greek Government Gazette (Issue B’ 6983/19.12.2024) [21] which includes the NECP was considered.

The results of this study reveal that Greece already has a well established LTRS and significant progress was made towards the NBRP, particularly regarding the overview of the national building stock (data included in Section A of Annex II of the EPBD), with comprehensive information on building types, energy performance certificates and energy consumption details but without any specific reference to the surface of these buildings. However, gaps are identified mainly in areas such as the annual renovation rates which are in progress and in zero-emission building thresholds. It should be noted that a great part of these gaps relates to newer

requirements introduced in the revised EPBD [4] that were not part of the regulatory framework when Greece's LTRS was published in 2021.

Slovenia:

Figure 5. Visualization of the checklist-based evaluation of Slovenia for Long Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS, circles) and National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP, diamonds). Each vertical line represents a mandatory item delineated in the Annex II of the EPBD in the template for the development of NBRP. The x-axis presents each item's code; descriptions and corresponding items are provided in the appendix. Results are displayed as points positioned within "adequate," "incomplete," or "missing" zones. The dashed line in the "adequate" zone indicates ideal compliance.

To complete the checklist, Slovenia's LTRS were reviewed, with progress assessed using internal data from the Energy Efficiency Centre at the Jožef Stefan Institute, responsible for the updated LTRS. Comparison with the new EPBD 2024 framework highlights that while Slovenia's previous LTRS provided a solid overview of the building stock and set high-level targets for 2030 and 2050, it lacked the detailed breakdowns now required—such as disaggregation by energy class, ownership, and performance tier, as well as clear treatment of worst-performing and exempted buildings.

Policy content in the earlier LTRS was mostly descriptive, with limited quantification and only partial coverage of renovation passports, public building actions, and financing mechanisms. The revised EPBD, however, demands more granular data, enforceable measures, and explicit links to zero-emission building standards, as well as clearly defined investment needs through 2050 [15]. These discrepancies become evident towards the end of the graph, where several items rated as adequate for the LTRS appear as missing when evaluating the most recent NBRP developments.

In summary, while Slovenia's previous LTRS established ambitions and macro-targets, the 2024 EPBD requires a far more data-driven and actionable approach. Updating the LTRS will necessitate both new data and structural revisions to meet the directive's focus on measurable impacts, enforceability, and integration of cross-cutting issues such as energy poverty and resilience.

Spain:

Figure 6. Visualization of the checklist-based evaluation of Spain for Long Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS, circles). Each vertical line represents a mandatory item delineated in the Annex II of the EPBD in the template for the development of NBRP. The x-axis presents each item's code; descriptions and corresponding items are provided in the appendix. Results are displayed as points positioned within “adequate,” “incomplete,” or “missing” zones. The dashed line in the “adequate” zone indicates ideal compliance.

For the assessment of Spain's LTRS, the corresponding document entitled ‘ERESEE 2020’ [22] has been used. Data for the assessment of the current on-going status of the NBRP was not available and therefore not included. The Spanish strategy ERESEE 2020 constitutes a solid and technically detailed reference for building renovation planning at the national level. It is particularly strong in the characterization of the building stock and in the inventory of policies and programs, including financial instruments, addressing energy poverty and market barriers [15]. However, alignment with EPBD will require substantial revisions in key areas. These include: the establishment of GHG-based ZEB thresholds, the introduction of MEPS for non-residential buildings, the specification of quantitative investment needs for 2030–2050, and the definition of a trajectory for residential energy performance with a clear milestone for 2035.

The current analysis of Spain's renovation strategies highlights both notable strengths and areas needing further improvement. While the ERESEE 2020 strategy provides a thorough national reference, substantial updates will be necessary to achieve full compliance with the latest requirements of the revised directive. A favorable starting point for these adjustments is provided by the existence of robust data and established institutional mechanisms, as long as adequate regulatory and budgetary commitments are ensured in the upcoming national renovation plan.

5. Conclusion

Each country's contribution to the proposed assessment reflects a systematic approach benchmarked to the latest available provisions on NBRP to verify the current status of individual indicators delineated in the Annex II of the revised EPBD [4]. This process enabled case study countries to identify gaps and areas needing improvement in their current LTRS, supporting their transition toward more comprehensive and effective NBRP.

While most countries demonstrated advances in documenting their building stock and establishing targets, the analysis also highlighted persistent gaps—particularly in areas such as

financing mechanisms and treatment of worst-performing buildings. Many of these gaps come from necessary efforts for the integration of new EPBD requirements introduced after the publication of earlier LTRS, demanding standardized indicators, more detailed data, identified needs and measurable targets for the implementation of NBRP.

Throughout the assessment, items generally classified as “adequate” or “incomplete” in the LTRS but labelled as “missing” in the NBRP were due to the lack of detailed breakdowns required by the EPBD. However, identifying missing elements does not necessarily indicate backward steps; it may instead reflect items still under review for inclusion in the final NBRP version.

Among the countries assessed, Austria and Slovenia presented the fewest adequate items for NBRP implementation at the time of this study and thus face greater efforts to achieve an adequate NBRP. Spain, while not including an analysis of its latest NBRP developments, presents a solid LTRS evaluation with many adequate items, similar to Greece. The Flanders region of Belgium shows an improved overall adequacy of its NBRP. No clear cross-country pattern emerges across all examined case studies, but it is evident—and intuitive—that countries with stronger LTRS frameworks tend to show more adequate progress towards their NBRP goals.

The mandatory use of the EPBD’s standardized template for NBRPs represents a critical step toward improving the quality, comparability, and transparency of renovation plans across the EU. To ensure effective implementation, MS must address the identified gaps by enhancing data collection, clarifying regulatory frameworks, and securing adequate financing. Timely submission and regular updates of NBRPs, aligned with NECPs, will be essential for tracking progress and ensuring that the EU building stock is on a viable pathway toward climate neutrality by 2050. Ultimately, success will depend on sustained political commitment, robust monitoring, and the capacity to translate strategic planning into large-scale, effective renovation actions.

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Glossary of Abbreviations

- **EPBD:** Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
- **MS:** European Union Member States
- **NBRP:** National Building Renovation Plan
- **LTRS:** Long-Term Renovation Strategy (or Long-Term Renovation Strategies)
- **NECP:** National Energy and Climate Plan

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Appendix: Legend codes used in Figures 2–6 correspond to mandatory items from Annex II of the EPBD [4]. Item titles have been abbreviated for conciseness.

Annex II - EPBD - EU/2024/1275		Annex II - EPBD - EU/2024/1275	
codes - items	items -	codes - items	items -
A	Overview of the national building stock	C	Overview of implemented and planned policies and measures
A.1	Number of buildings and total floor area (m²)	C.1.1	Policies and measures with regard to the following elements:
A.1/1	per building type (including public buildings and social housing)	C.1.1/a	cost-eff. appr. to renovation for diff. building types/ climate zones - potential relevant trigger points in the life cycle of the building;
A.1/2	per energy performance class	C.1.1/b	national min. energy perf. standards, policies to target the worst-performing segments of the national building stock
A.1/3	nearly zero-energy buildings	C.1.1/c	promotion of deep renovation of buildings, including staged deep
A.1/4	worst-performing buildings (including a definition)	C.1.1/d	empowering and protecting vulnerable customers and the alleviation of energy poverty, including policies and measures
A.1/5	the 43 % worst-performing residential buildings	C.1.1/e	the creation of one-stop shops or similar mechanisms for the provision of technical, administrative and financial advice and assistance;
A.1/6	estimation of the share of buildings exempted	C.1.1/f	the decarbonisation of heating and cooling, including district networks, phasing out fossil fuels, targeting boiler phase-out by 2040.
A.2	Number of energy performance certificates	C.1.1/g	prevention and treatment of construction and demolition waste, prioritizing the waste hierarchy and circular economy goals.
A.2/1	per building type (including public buildings)	C.1.1/h	promotion of renewables in buildings to meet the sector's indicative renewable energy target.
A.2/2	per energy performance class	C.1.1/i	the deployment of solar energy installations on buildings;
A.3	Annual renovation rates: number and total floor area (m²)	C.1.1/j	reduction of WLC GHG emissions across buildings' lifecycle and increased carbon removals.
A.3/1	per building type	C.1.1/k	promotion of integrated district-level renovation programmes on energy, mobility, waste, water, urban plan., local resources, circularity,
A.3/2	to nearly zero-energy and/or to zero-emission building levels	C.1.1/l	the improvement of buildings owned by public bodies, including policies and measures
A.3/3	per renovation depth (weighted average renovation)	C.1.1/m	promotion of smart technologies and infrastructure for sustainable mobility in buildings
A.3/4	public buildings	C.1.1/n	addressing market barriers and market failures;
A.4.1	Primary and final annual energy consumption (ktoe)	C.1.1/o	Address skills gaps and promote educ., training, (re/up)skilling in const., energy efficiency and renewables for skilled building workforce
A.4.1/1	per building type	C.1.1/p	awareness-raising campaigns and other advisory tools
A.4.1/1	per end use	C.1.1/q	promotion of modular and industrialised solutions for construction and building renovation
A.4.2	Energy savings (ktoe)	C.1.2	For all policies and measures
A.4.2/1	residential buildings	C.1.2/1	name of policy or measure
A.4.2/2	non-residential buildings	C.1.2/2	short description (precise scope, objective and conditions of operation)
A.4.2/3	public buildings	C.1.2/3	quantified objective
A.4.3	Average primary energy use in kWh/(m².y) for residential buildings	C.1.2/4	type of policy or measure
A.4.4	Share of renewable energy in the building sector (MW installed or GWh generated):	C.1.2/5	planned budget and funding sources
A.4.4/1	for different uses	C.1.2/6	entities responsible for implementing the policy
A.5.1	Annual operational greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂eq/(m².y))	C.1.2/7	expected impact
A.5.1/1	per building type	C.1.2/8	status of implementation
A.5.2	Annual operational greenhouse gas emission reduction (kgCO₂eq/(m².y))	C.1.2/9	date of entry into force
A.5.2/1	per building type	C.1.2/1	Implementation period
A.6.1	Market barriers and failures (description):	D	Outline of the investments needs, the budgetary sources and the administrative resources
A.6.1/1	split incentives	D/1	total investment needs for 2030, 2040, 2050 (million EUR)
A.6.1/2	capacity of construction and energy sector	D/2	public investments (million EUR)
A.6.2	Evaluation of the capacities in the construction, energy efficiency and renewable energy sectors	D/3	private investments (million EUR)
A.7	Energy poverty (definition)	D/4	budgetary resources
A.7/1	% of people affected by energy poverty	E	Thresholds of new and renovated zero-emission buildings, referred to in Article 11
A.7/2	proportion of disposable household income spent on energy	E/1	operational greenhouse gas emissions thresholds of new zero-emission buildings;
A.7/3	population living in inadequate dwelling conditions	E/2	operational greenhouse gas emissions thresholds of renovated zero-emission buildings;
A.8	Primary energy factors	E/3	annual primary energy use thresholds of new zero-emission buildings;
A.8/1	per energy carrier	E/4	annual primary energy use thresholds of renovated zero-emission
A.8/2	non-renewable primary energy factor	F	Minimum energy performance standards for non-residential buildings
A.8/3	renewable primary energy factor	F/1	maximum energy performance thresholds, pursuant to Article 9(1)
A.8/4	total primary energy factor	G	National trajectory for the progressive renovation of the residential building stock
A.9	Definition of nearly-zero energy building for new and existing buildings	G/1	national trajectory for the prog. renovation of the res. building stock, with 2030 and 2035 milestones for average primary energy use in kWh/(m ² .y)
A.10	Cost-optimal minimum energy performance requirements for new and existing buildings		
B	Roadmap for 2030, 2040, 2050		
B.1.1	Targets for annual renovation rates: number and total floor area (m²)		
B.1.1/1	per building type		
B.1.1/2	worst-performing buildings		
B.1.1/3	the 43 % worst-performing residential buildings		
B.1.2	Information pursuant to Article 9(1)		
B.1.2/1	criteria to exempt individual non-residential buildings		
B.1.2/2	estimated share of exempted non-residential buildings		
B.1.2/3	equiv. energy perf.e improvements - exempted non-res. buildings		
B.2.1	Targets for expected primary and final annual energy consumption (ktoe)		
B.2.1/1	per building type		
B.2.1/2	per end use		
B.2.2	Expected energy savings		
B.2.2/1	per building type		
B.2.3	Targets for the increase in the share of renewable energy in accordance with Article 15a of Directive (EU) 2018/2001		
B.2.4	Numerical targets for the deployment of solar energy in buildings		
B.3.1	Targets for expected operational greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂eq/(m².y))		
B.3.1/1	per building type		
B.3.2	Targets for expected operational greenhouse gas emission reduction (%)		
B.3.2/1	per building type		
B.4.1	Expected wider benefits		
B.4.1/1	% reduction of people affected by energy poverty		
B.5	The Member State's contribution to the Union's energy efficiency targets in accordance with Article 4 of Directive (EU) 2023/1791 attributable to its building stock's renovation (share and figure in ktoe)		
B.6	The Member State's contribution to the Union's renewable energy targets in accordance with Directive (EU) 2018/2001 attributable to its building stock's renovation (share, MW installed or GWh generated)		